

IMPACT OF USAGE OF SOCIAL NETWORKING SITES AND STRESS AMONG PG STUDENTS OF CENTRAL UNIVERSITY OF PUNJAB

Ishfaq Majid
Research Scholar,
School of Education,
Central University of Gujarat
Email: Panditishfaq786@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The present study was conducted to explore the influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites and Stress among PG students of Central University of Punjab. The objectives of the study were to find out the level of Usage of Social Networking Sites and Stress, relationship of Usage of Social Networking Sites and Stress among Male, Female and Science, Humanities streams of PG Students. The total number of 200 students were selected by using stratified random sampling technique for the collection of data. Data was collected by using Self-made questionnaire on Usage of Social Networking Sites and Stress Scale by Pallavi Bhatnagar, Megha Singh, Manoj Pandey, Sandhya and Amitabh (2015). The study found that maximum number of PG Students of Central University of Punjab comes under moderate level of usage of Social Networking Sites and Stress. The findings reveals that there is significant positive influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Stress. It was also revealed that there is no influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Stress among female PG students of Central University of Punjab. The study also reveals that there is no impact of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Stress among PG students of Humanities. It was also found that there is a no impact of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Stress among PG students of Science stream students of Central University of Punjab. Moreover, there is no significant difference in the usage of Social Networking Sites among PG students of Science and Humanities streams.

Keywords: Social Networking Sites, Stress, Virtual Private Network, CUPB

INTRODUCTION

The 21st century is the world of technology where most people do not even imagine their life without technology. Modern communication technology has undoubtedly transformed the whole world into a "global community". It helps people learn better, have an open mind and stay informed with global growth. Technology reveals to humanity a better way of doing things. Even today begins with the alarm on the phone and ends with the application messages on the smart phone, this situation also prevails in most of the rural areas. The use of technology in the classroom has two sides, as well as coins, both positive and negative. Most schools place more emphasis on computer education and the use of mobile learning because the use of this technology in today's classroom helps students to participate, learn actively, work to the needs of student and receive feedback from an expert teacher. But most schools

do not allow their students to use mobile devices because they think that by using this type of technology, students

become technology-dependent and take less participation in face-to-face interaction with parents, teachers and colleagues who play a role. Crucial role in improving social skills. Bandura gives primary importance to observation. According to Bandura's theory, children learn by observing their classmates, teachers and parents. For example, children start walking as when the father walks because they observe them. Bandura emphasis on social skills that can be acquired by interacting with society in today's age, we discover that young students always interact with their technological toys, even most of the traffic accident is due to the use of the mobile phone during their journey.

1.1 Social Networking Sites

Social networking sites refer to various applications, websites or new online media that allows large numbers of individuals to share their information and develop a proper social and specialized contact. The various social networking sites are Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram, snapshot, Youtube, and blogs.

Social networking sites (SNS) are online services that emphasize the creation of a connection between people to enable them to share their interests. These network sites allow people to share their information in a particular group. Therefore, the main purpose of the social networking sites is to allow people to share their real-life interests, activities and experiences. Social networks refer mainly to the means used for interaction, which have become phenomena of growth in the social and academic field. Social media allows people and organizations to create, participate and share new or existing content through multi-way communication. Commonly, the phrase "social network sites" is used as a general term for all social networks, including Facebook, Twitter and Myspace. Over the past decade, every social networking application has worked collaboratively to provide a completely new multimedia experience that can now be accessed via mobile devices.

Social networks have become a very important part of our personal and professional life. In a day we dedicate a few hours of our time to social networks, commenting, publishing, etc. Social networks are spreading the product of various popular social networking platforms. Today, social networking sites are widely used by millions of people. The web provides a means to search for information. Many people have discovered that the Internet can be used to connect with many other people, either for commercial or commercial reasons, to make new friends or to awaken old friends and relatives long lost some time ago. SNS is web-based services that, within a limited system, individuals can allow the creation of a semi-profile and a complete list of new users with which they share their views, associations and points of view. Social networking websites contain over 100,000,000 registered users. Most of the users of SNS are young, which have been called 'Digital Citizens'.

The most common users are students of higher education. Students often use social networks to stay in touch with their friends or strengthen existing connections instead of developing new relationships. Students regularly publish inappropriate content for all types of audiences, especially for potential employers (Miller et. al., 2010). SNS is virtual community where people can create individual profiles for audience use, interact with friends but not face to face, but at a distance and can establish a relationship with other people of the same shared interest. They are considered a phenomenon with an exponential increase in use in recent years. The great appeal of social networks on the Internet can said to be a major concern as individuals are spending more and more time to use these social networks. People are interested in different types of Internet activities; some people can be addictive instead of becoming addictive to be the medium. Some users could develop a dependency on the particular activities that they perform on-line. As per some views there are five different types of Internet addiction (eg Computer addiction), information overload (dependence on web browsing) and dependence on cybernetic relationships (e.g. dependence on online interaction). The dependency on social networking sites seems to fall into the latter category. Given the fact that the main purpose and motivation for using social networking sites is to establish and maintain relationships both online and offline.

From the perspective of a clinical psychologist, it might be reasonable to talk specifically about addiction to Facebook because addiction measures, such as abandonment of personal life, mental worry, avoidance, tolerance, experiences that change the state Encouragement and concealment of addictive behavior, the request to be present in some people who use social networking sites. Hundreds of millions of users now contribute content from social networks using Web 2.0 and SNS handles like Facebook and Twitter. Social media is a platform where users can search for the desired contents of the network, share their experience and establish a relationship for various purposes, social or educational. Human beings are social creatures. They need to communicate with others and have to be a part of our nature. Today we constantly interact with family and colleagues on various occasions, either by necessity or simply for satisfaction. The development of science and technology, communication and networking opportunities have changed a lot. In modern times there has been an outbreak of social networks since the beginning of the mobile phone and the Internet until the creation of websites such as Facebook and Twitter, and they have all been integrated into our lives today. Furthermore, the growth of mobile devices, including smartphones and tablets, has brought the social network world directly within our reach, making it a valuable tool for politicians in particular. SNS have become resources for political news, information and a source of electoral reach before the elections. However, these new technologies help us communicate with people from all over the world. With an increasing number of people, especially teenagers, who use the Internet to socialize with friends, connect with appropriate people or even use it as a place to express their feelings, SNS have become a tool for problems like addiction. Social network addiction is used to refer to someone who spends too most of his time using Facebook, Twitter and new forms of social networks to interfere with other aspects of everyday life. There is no authorized medical examination of social network

addiction as an illness or ailment. Addiction can be defined as a compulsive behavior that leads to negative effects and harmful results. In most addictions, people are supposed to perform those kind of activities so frequently that they became a harmful habit of them, which then interfered with other activities such as employment or institution. In this situation, an employee from social media can be measured by someone who cannot help but use social networks to continuously access Facebook status updates or "haunt" people's profile on Facebook. Social networks, is the obligation of citizens who use social networks to decide what is right or wrong. It is the duty of citizens not to blindly follow all the information presented in social networks and you should always check it from other sources. Social networks are here to stay, and it is a duty of our young generations to see that it plays a unique role in improving society and our nation in general. Social networks have become one of the most important media in modern times. However, social networks exist to provide communication between citizens regardless of distance, make them accessible to people enables them to share information, documents and videos, generate blogs, send messages and perform real-time discussions. These systems are discussed at the same time as social media, essentially because they can enable communication with friends and partners in a fluid and efficient way. It also strengthens the connections between people in those systems. The favorite in the realm of Internet sites is Facebook, Twitter, Whatsapp, Instagram and others. These websites and social opportunities are the means of direct communication with other people on a social level and in the media. They are playing an important and significant role in making decisions on the occasions of universal civilization in an economic, political, social and educational way. There were several general ideas and ideas that accepted four main advantages of using social networks in higher education. These consist of improving connection, improving educational inspiration, offering modified teaching materials and developing cooperative skills. It means that this type of activities of social networks has the chance to increase student contacts with their friends and colleagues. SNS is the main application under authority of social media that comes with Web 2.0 era. Today the Social networks are considered the quickest growing web application in the 21st century. The large number of applications such as Wiki, streaming, video applications and social networks has made it easy to stream online videos. Facebook users have surpassed all social media applications with over nine hundred fifty-five million users in 2013, followed by Twitter with five hundred million users. In addition, the age distribution of Facebook users is focused on younger groups, where 300 million users are between 18 and 24 years old and 120 million users between 13 and 17 years. The previous site indicated an almost equal distribution of users between men and women. Finally, at the end of 2012, Jordan had 2.5 million Facebook users, with a similar size of Internet users (www.internetworldstats.com). Through social networks, we can stay in touch with members of our family who do not live near us. Families have been changed to the extended family and community life has significantly reduced in many cultures. Social networks have invited people to their lives. In America, a survey reported that 84% of young people in the United States have a Facebook account (O'Keeffe, 2017).

Brissette (2002) conducted a study on the role of optimism in the development of social networks, coping and psychological adaptation and found that university students of both sexes completed measures of perceived stress, depression, network of friendship and social perception. Coping was evaluated at the end of the first half. Greater optimism, assessed at the beginning of the first semester of the university, was prospectively associated with lower increases in stress and depression and greater increases in perceived social support (but not in the size of the friendship network) during the first semester of university.

The growth of social networks over the years has transformed the way many users experience the Internet. Gone are the days when the Internet was used as a one-way transmission system where users only downloaded data, information from a limited number of content providers. This sense of Internet use has changed the definition of social networks that is now described in terms of collaboration, coexistence and creativity. As pictures now the Internet is certainly very different from that of 10 years before. Among all these technological developments, it is been thought that educators are expected to prepare themselves with the world of new social media applications and users of social networks that are mostly university students. The opportunities offered by social networks to collaborate, establish contacts, share knowledge and content is considered best for higher education studies. It is the reliable source for teachers to be in contact with their students in the campus. With the help of Social networks, teachers are able to share information with their students by creating groups. Therefore, it is important that higher level educators can approach social networks in a considered and objective way.

Social networks have become international development and have extended their coverage to almost every corner of the world. With these improvements, there is great concern because in this era of great technological development, social networking sites are increasingly popular among students, especially in India. It is known that the use of social networks has not only attracted the attention of academics but researchers also. Over 60% of young people between 13 and 17 years old have a minimal social network profile and many spend more than two hours a day on social networks. Lack et. al. (2009) reported in his study that most of the students who use social networking sites, can easily access other user profiles by using their account information discussable in public accounts suggest that formal education should be presided over by students regarding the use of these sites.

The observers have enlisted a variety of both positive and negative impacts of the use of social networks. Social media can be an effective communication tool (or advertising) for companies, business people, non-profit organizations, including groups that support parties and governments. On a similar occasion, concerns were expressed about possible links between the use of heavy social media and despair, and even the problems of cyberbullying: online bothering and trolling. Currently, about half of adolescent adults have been cybernetically molested together with individual Chapin John, (2016). Petteret. al. (2009) reported in his study that peoples and college student's uses social networking sites by several motivational reasons. In spite, the study has made several attempts to understand the choice, use, dispersal, adoption and acceptance of social networking sites among university students.

There are several reasons why people use a social networking site. One of the reasons is that they meet strangers and become friends. Through social networking sites, users can keep their interpersonal relationship with their friends and users can send private messages, can use chat rooms and other methods of communication (Vitak, 2008)

1.2 Stress

Today, the stress levels among children is rising very fast due to the pressure of their academic or cultural activities. Not all children are able to cope with such high expectations and parents do not seem to realize or accept that their children are under strong pressure, "says Elizabeth Vadakhakkara, child psychologist and director of Thrani (The Hindu, 2003).

Stress can be defined as the total response of an organism to environmental demands or pressures. The term stress was first studied in 1950s, the term to indicate both the causes and the effects of these pressures which a person is receiving. A recurrent disagreement between the investigations refers to the definition of stress in humans. Stress is defined as a disturbance of the homeostasis of the body. This request in the body-mind occurs when it attempts to deal with the incessant changes in life.

Women have experienced more stress than men because of frustration, self-imposed stress and pressure. It has been found that academic stress due to changes, conflicts and frustrations only occasionally causes stress to students (Misra et. al., 2000). Stress, inadequate social support and coping were linked to higher levels of depression and less life satisfaction in both men and women (Asberg, 2005). 13.6% of the student population examined had symptoms of depression, 25.6% had symptoms of anxiety and 26% had symptoms of stress, ranging from mild to extremely (Jovanovic 2017). Abused wives obtained higher scores in terms of depression, anxiety and stress than unused abusers. (Fadardi, 2009).

1.2.1 Effect of Stress

When a human being is in a difficult situation, the brain stimulates the body and prepares it for defensive action by releasing stress hormones, such as cortisone and adrenaline. These hormones in the blood are depleted, which implies reduced effects on stress and anxiety symptoms.

When our body cannot counteract a new stress situation, hormones and chemicals remain unpublished in the blood for a long time. It results in physical symptoms related to stress. Like tension, muscles, fuzzy anxiety, and dizziness and accelerated heartbeat. Internet addiction directly affects depression, anxiety and stress. Students with a high Internet addiction are more likely to be vulnerable to depression, anxiety and stress (Ahmet and Murat, 2017).

Stress may increase the risk of both acute and chronic psychosomatic illness and weaken the immune system. When this system weakens, the body loses its ability to fight these diseases and, slowly, the power of resistance is reduced. It leads to different types of problems in the body such as infections, arthritis, allergy, bronchitis, asthma, etc. In a study conducted on

factors associated with depression, anxiety and stress among students of the professional medical school, it was found that 13.6% of the student population examined had symptoms of depression, 25.6% had symptoms of anxiety and 26% had symptoms of stress, ranging from mild to extremely (Jovanovic, 2017)

Taylor and his colleagues (S.E. Taylor, Kellin, et al., 2000) have developed a theory of stress responses called Tender and Friend. The theory holds that, in addition to fighting or fleeing, humans respond to stress with social and nutritional behaviour. These responses can be particularly characteristic of women. Because the men were responsible for finding food and taking care of the children. Because caring for offspring, particularly in times of stress, is a complex task, the theory of bonding claims that being friends is, joining others and seeking social contact during stress can be particularly characteristic of women and can help self-preservation and protection of the offspring. Like the fight or flight mechanism, tenderness and friendship can depend in particular on the underlying biological mechanism, oxytocin may be important for the female response to stress.

1.2.1.1 Types of Stress

There are different types of stress:

Acute stress

Acute stress is usually short-term and may be due to work pressure, compliance with periods of pressure or a miner's accident due to stress, increased physical activity, looking for something but its loss, or similar things.

Symptoms of this type of tension are headaches, backaches, stomach problems, rapid heartbeat or pain in the body.

Episodic acute stress

Acute episodic stress is known to be common in people who have too many responsibilities and are overloaded or overloaded with work, disorganized, always in a hurry and never on time. These people generally occupy important positions in their workplace and the stressful lifestyle is intrinsic to them.

Symptoms of this type of stress are prolonged tension headaches, hypertension, migraine, chest pain and heart disease.

Chronic Stress

This type of stress is the most serious of all three stress type. Chronic stress is a prolonged stress that exists for weeks, months, or even years. This stress is due to poverty, broken or stressed families and marriages, chronic illness stem from traumatic, early childhood experiences that become formalized and remain forever painful and present. People suffering from this type of stress get used to it and may even not realize that they are under

chronic stress. Chronic strain may influence the relationship between specific stressors and adverse physical or psychological effects.

Coping with Stress

There are many things we can do to help our self-esteem. For things that happen every day, it can be helpful to think of our stress as a puzzle to solve. Stress management includes that kind of technique which invented to provide a person with effective mechanisms to deal with psychological stress and stress defines a person's psychological response to an internal or external stimulus that triggers the response to combat or flight. Stress management is effective when a person uses strategies to deal with or change situations. There are several ways to deal with stress, how to control the source of stress or learn to set limits and say "No" to some requests that bases or family members can take.

The ability of a person to tolerate the source of stress can be increased by thinking of another topic, such as a hobby, listening to music or spending time in the desert. List all the things we can think of making life easier or less stressful by writing them down on a piece of paper. This can help make things short in our head.

Stress can be positive

The word "Positive" and stress often do not go hand in hand. But there are countless cases of athletes who face the challenge of stress and reach the unattainable, scientists strive to bring to light the most unthinkable secrets of the phenomenal world, and also painter, composer of a writer who produces the best paintings. Psychologists give us the second opinion that some stressful situations can actually increase our inner potential and can be creatively useful.

Sudha Chandran an Indian dancer lost both legs in an accident. But the physical and social deficiencies have given him more momentum to continue with his dance performances with the help of prosthetic legs.

Stress is not always necessarily harmful. Stress Inspire Creative Successful work that is beneficial, while that of the failure, humiliation or infection is harmful. Stress can be negative or positive. Passing is a test that can be stressful as a failure. At some point we know in advance that doing something will be stressful, but we are willing to do it. For example, when planning a holiday in a mountain resort, we know it would be stressful at times. But we are willing to face these challenges. Experts tell us that stress, in a moderate way, is necessary in our life. Stress responses are one of the best systems of defence of our body against external and internal dangers.

Rationale of the study

Social Networking Sites (SNS) has become a subject of importance since the promotion of social media marked the shift of producer generated content towards user-generated content. In the context of technology enhanced learning, this paradigm change marks the shift from class e-learning, based on courses and the sequential presentation of learning material, towards a more active participation of the learners and the support of the learners as a community of interest. On the basis of reviews the researcher find that Social Networking Sites are Web-based platforms on which individuals connect with other users to generate and maintain social connections. Some reviews are showing that users use Social Networking Sites for enjoyment. But some reviews shows that use of SNSs may lead to stress. On one hand, SNSs may protect from mental illness, as they support and enable social interaction and allow users to reflect aspects of their identity and express emotion that may be relevant to their life experience. On the other hand, there are many opportunities for miscommunications and mismanaged expectations and maladaptive tendencies can be exaggerated, leaving individuals feeling a greater sense of isolation. Central University of Punjab (CUPB) is a university where students from all over the country join for their future studies. Almost all the students of Central University of Punjab are using Social Networking Sites despite ban by the authorities. Still students use Social Networking Sites by using VPN showing the addiction of students towards Social Media. Hence my research work got an opportunity to explore the negative effect of Social Networking Sites like Stress on students of Central University of Punjab. So the main focus of my research will be how the usage of Social Networking Sites leads to stress among the Post Graduate students of CUPB.

Objectives

The study under investigation has the following objectives;

1. To study the level of usage of Social Networking Sites among PG Students of Central University of Punjab
2. To examine the level of Stress among PG Students of Central University of Punjab
3. To explore the influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Stress among Male PG Students of Central University of Punjab
4. To explore the influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Stress among Female PG Students of Central University of Punjab
5. To study the impact of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Stress among PG Students of Humanities Stream of Central University of Punjab
6. To study the impact of usage of Social Networking Sites on Stress among PG Students of Science stream of Central University of Punjab
7. To compare the usage of Social Networking Sites of male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab.
8. To compare the usage of Social Networking Sites among PG students of Science and Humanities streams of Central University of Punjab.

9. To compare the level of Stress among PG students of Science and Humanities stream of Central University of Punjab

10. To compare the level of Stress among male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab

Hypotheses of the study

The study under investigation has the following hypotheses;

1. Majority of PG Students of Central University of Punjab will come under higher level of usage of Social Networking Sites
2. Majority of PG Students of Central University of Punjab will depict low level of Stress.
3. There will be no significant influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Stress among Male PG Students of Central University of Punjab
4. There will be no significant influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Stress among Female PG Students of Central University of Punjab
5. Usage of Social Networking Sites will put no significant impact on Stress among PG Students of Humanities Stream of Central University of Punjab
6. Usage of Social Networking Sites will put no significant impact on Stress among PG Students of Science stream of Central University of Punjab
7. There will be no significant difference in the usage of Social Networking Sites among the male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab.
8. There will be no significant difference in the usage of Social Networking Sites among PG students of Science and Humanities streams of Central University of Punjab.

Delimitations of the study

- The study was delimited to four Humanities and four Science Departments of Central University of Punjab.
- The Sample size was delimited to 200 students of Humanities and Science Stream of Central University of Punjab.
- The Sample size was further delimited to 100 male and 100 female PG students of Central University of Punjab.

METHOD AND PROCEDURE

In the present study, the researcher used the descriptive method of research that is based on observation as a process of data collection. In the present study, Social Networking Sites is independent variable while as Stress is Dependent variable.

Sample

In the present study, a sample of 200 post graduate students was taken and then classified according to their flows. The sample was further divided into gender wise and stream wise.

Sampling Technique

For the present study, the researcher used the stratified random sampling technique for the collection of data. Data were collected from the Central Punjab University, Bathinda.

Tools

For the present study, the following tools were used

I. Stress scale (2011) by Pallavi Bhatnagar, Megha Singh, Manoj Pandey, Sandhya and Amitabh.

II. Self-made Questionnaire on checking Usage of Social Networking Sites was developed by the investigator.

Technique of Analysis and Interpretation

Statistical techniques Percentage Analysis, Correlation and t-test were used for analysis and interpretation of data. In the present study the Percentage Analysis was used to check the level of Usage of SNS and Stress among PG students of Central University of Punjab. Correlation was used to analyse the of Usage of SNS on Stress among Male, Female, Science & Humanities students of Central University of Punjab and t-test was used to compare the means of Usage of SNS and Stress among male, Female, Science and Humanities post-graduate students of CUPB to analyse the level of significance.

RESULT, INTERPRETATION AND DISCUSSION

Hypothesis - 1: Majority of PG Students of Central University of Punjab will come under higher level of usage of Social Networking Sites

To study the level of usage of Social Networking Sites among PG Students of Central University of Punjab, the scores were obtained by administering the Self-made Questionnaire on Usage of Social Networking Sites. The results were interpreted and analysed by calculating the Low, Medium and High level of Usage of Social Networking Sites.

Table 1.1 shows the Level of usage of Social Networking Sites among PG Students of Central University of Punjab. It was revealed from table that out of 200 students, 18% of the PG students fall under higher level of Usage of Social Networking Sites, 68% fall in the moderate level and 14% fall in the Low level of Usage of Social Networking Sites. It was found that majority of the PG students of Central University of Punjab have moderate level of Usage of Social Networking Sites. Hence the hypothesis is rejected.

Table 1.1**Level of Usage of Social Networking Sites**

Usage of SNS	N	High Level of Usage of SNS	Moderate Level of Usage of SNS	Low Level of Usage of SNS
	200	18%	68%	14%

Hypothesis – 2: Majority of PG Students of Central University of Punjab will depict low level of Stress

To study the level of Stress among PG students of Central University of Punjab, the scores were obtained by administering the Anxiety, Stress and Depression Scale. The results of the analysed data are given in table 1.2 showing percentage of the level of Stress among PG students of Central University of Punjab.

Table 1.2 shows the level of Stress among PG students of Central University of Punjab. It was found that 16% fall under normal level of Stress, 16.5% fall under Mild level, 52% fall under moderate & 15.5% fall under severe level of Stress. Hence, it was found that maximum number of the PG students of Central University of Punjab have moderate level of Stress. Hence the hypothesis is rejected.

Table 1.2**Level of Stress among PG students of Central University of Punjab**

Level of Stress	N	Normal level of Stress	Mild level of Stress	Moderate level of Stress	Severe level of Stress
	200	16%	16.5%	52%	15.5%

Hypothesis – 3: There will be no significant influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Stress among Male PG Students of Central University of Punjab

To study the significant influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Stress among Male PG Students of Central University of Punjab, the scores obtained by administering the Self-made Questionnaire on Usage of Social Networking Sites and Stress Scale was analysed using correlation. The results of the analysed data are given in table 1.3 showing the ‘r’ value and level of significance with respect to Usage of Social Networking Sites and Stress respectively among male PG students of Central University of Punjab

Table 1.3, shows the coefficient of correlation between Usage of Social Networking Sites and Stress among male PG students of Central University of Punjab. It was found that the r-value

of Usage of Social Networking Sites and stress of male students of Central University of Punjab is 0.0713 which is less than table value of r with the df of 200 at 0.05 i.e. 198. Hence r -value is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence it can be interpreted that from the table 3.8 & 3.9, the coefficient of correlation is positive, so there is a significant positive influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Stress among male PG students of Central University of Punjab. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 1.3

Coefficient of Correlation between Usage of Social Networking Sites and Stress among male PG students of Central University of Punjab

Variables	N	df	'r' value	Level of Significance	Remarks
Usage of SNS	100	198	0.0713	< 0.05	Positive Correlation
Stress	100				

Hypothesis – 4: There will be no significant influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Stress among Female PG Students of Central University of Punjab

To study the significant influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Stress among female PG Students of Central University of Punjab, the scores obtained by administering the Self-made Questionnaire on Usage of Social Networking Sites and Stress Scale was analysed using correlation. The results of the analysed data are given in table 1.4 showing the ' r ' value and level of significance with respect to Usage of Social Networking Sites and Stress respectively among female PG students of Central University of Punjab

Table 1.4 shows the coefficient of correlation between Usage of Social Networking Sites and Stress among female PG students of Central University of Punjab. It was found the r -value of Usage of Social Networking Sites and stress of female students of Central University of Punjab is -0.2067 which is less than table value of r with the df of 200 at 0.05 i.e. 198. Hence r -value is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence it can be interpreted that the coefficient of correlation is negative, so there is a no influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Stress among female PG students of Central University of Punjab.

Table 1.4

Coefficient of Correlation between Usage of Social Networking Sites and Stress among Female PG students of Central University of Punjab

Variables	N	df	'r' value	Level of Significance	Remarks
Usage of SNS	100	198	-0.2067	< 0.05	Negative Correlation
Stress	100				

Hypothesis – 5: Usage of Social Networking Sites will put no significant impact on Stress among PG Students of Humanities Stream of Central University of Punjab

To study the Impact of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Stress among PG Students of Humanities Stream of Central University of Punjab, the scores obtained by administering the Self-made Questionnaire on Usage of Social Networking Sites and Stress Scale were analysed using correlation. The results of the analysed data are given in table 1.5 showing the 'r' value and level of significance with respect to Usage of Social Networking Sites and Stress among PG students of Humanities Stream of Central University of Punjab.

Table 1.5 shows the coefficient of correlation between Usage of Social Networking Sites and Stress among PG students of Humanities Stream of Central University of Punjab. It was revealed from that the r-value of Usage of Social Networking Sites and stress among PG students of Humanities stream of CUPB is 0.0713 which is less than table value of r with the df of 200 at 0.05 i.e. 198. Hence r-value is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence it can be interpreted that the coefficient of correlation is negative, so there is a no impact of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Stress among PG students of Humanities stream students of CUPB. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 1.5

Coefficient of Correlation between Usage of Social Networking Sites and Stress among PG Students of Humanities Stream of CUPB

Variables	N	df	'r' value	Level of Significance	Remarks
Usage of SNS	100	198	-0.0312	< 0.05	Negative Correlation
Stress	100				

Hypothesis – 6: Usage of Social Networking Sites will put no significant impact on Stress among PG Students of Science stream of Central University of Punjab

To study the Impact of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Stress among PG Students of Science Stream of Central University of Punjab, the scores obtained by administering the Self-made Questionnaire on Usage of Social Networking Sites and Scale on Stress were analysed using correlation. The results of the analysed data are given in table 1.6 showing the 'r' value and level of significance with respect to Usage of Social Networking Sites and Stress among PG students of science Stream of Central University of Punjab.

Table 1.6 shows the coefficient of correlation between Usage of Social Networking Sites and Stress among PG students of Science Stream of Central University of Punjab. It was revealed that the r-value of Usage of Social Networking Sites and stress of PG students of Science stream of CUPB is -0.0239 which is less than table value of r with the df of 200 at 0.05 i.e. 198. Hence r-value is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence it can be interpreted that from the coefficient of correlation is negative, so there is a no impact of Usage of Social Networking

Sites on Stress among PG students of Science stream students of CUPB. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 1.6

Coefficient of Correlation between Usage of Social Networking Sites and Stress among PG Students of Science Stream of CUPB

Variables	N	df	'r' value	Level of Significance	Remarks
Usage of SNS	100	198	-0.0239	< 0.05	Negative Correlation
Stress	100				

Hypothesis – 7: There will be no significant difference in the usage of Social Networking Sites among the male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab

To study the difference between the usage of Social Networking Sites among the male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab, the scores obtained by administering the Questionnaire on Usage of social networking sites was analysed using t-test. The results of the analysed data are given in table 1.7 showing the mean, SD, t-value and level of significance with respect to usage of Social Networking Sites among the male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab

Table 1.7 shows the Mean, S.D, t- value and level of significance of usage of Social Networking Sites among male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab. It was revealed that the mean value of Usage of social networking sites of male and female are 86.88 and 86.78 respectively. The S.D. of male students is 7.67 and that of female students is 5.96. Also the calculated t-value is 0.10 which is less than table value of t with the df 198 at 0.05 level i.e. 1.98. Hence, it is concluded that the t-value is not significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted i.e. there is no significant difference between usage of Social Networking Sites among male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab.

Table 1.7:

Comparison of usage of Social Networking Sites among the male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab

Variables	N	Mean	S.D.	't' value	Level of significance
Male	100	86.88	7.67	0.10	< 0.05
Female	100	86.78	5.96		

Hypothesis – 8: There will be no significant difference in the usage of Social Networking Sites among PG students of Science and Humanities streams of Central University of Punjab.

To study the difference between the usage of Social Networking Sites among PG students of Science and Humanities streams of Central University of Punjab, the scores obtained by administering the Self-made Questionnaire on Usage of social networking sites was analysed using t-test. The results of the analysed data are given in table 3.22 showing the mean, SD, t-value and level of significance with respect to usage of Social Networking Sites among the male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab.

Table 1.8 shows the Mean, S.D, t- value and level of significance of usage of Social Networking Sites among PG students of Science and Humanities streams of Central University of Punjab. It was revealed that the mean value of Usage of social networking sites of Humanities and Science stream students are 87.56 and 86.1 respectively. The S.D. of Humanities student is 6.484 and that of Science students is 7.156. Also the calculated t-value is 1.50 which is less than table value of t with the df 198 at 0.05 level i.e. 1.98. Hence, it is concluded that the t-value is not significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted i.e. there is no significant difference between usage of Social Networking Sites among science and Humanities PG students of Central University of Punjab.

Table 1.8

Comparison of usage of Social Networking Sites among PG students of Science and Humanities streams of Central University of Punjab

Variables	N	Mean	S.D.	df	't' value	Level of significance
Humanities	100	87.56	6.484	198	1.50	< 0.05
Science	100	86.1	7.156			

CONCLUSION

Social Networking Sites have become part and parcel of our lives. With an increasing number of people, especially teenagers, who use the Internet to socialize with friends, connect with appropriate people or even use it as a place to express their feelings, SNS have become a tool for problems like addiction and similarly when going to the deep extent of this media, stress is a major issue that gets aroused. The students surfing the social media needs to be monitored about their usage. Despite the Universities are banning the surfing of these websites in their campuses still there is a need to ban the third party software's which help

students to access these websites. The students should be made aware about the possible problem related to social media. The investigator of the study is fully aware of the limitations under which the present research was conducted and therefore accepts that no broad conclusions could be made. These findings are only indicative of trends and hence following suggestions can be given for further research. The tool adopted for the present study was used as such without any modifications. The results of the study lack in external validity as the sample size was not large. The study was limited to post graduate students of Central University of Punjab.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

The investigator is fully aware of the limitations under which the present research was conducted and therefore accepts that no broad conclusions could be made. These findings are only indicative of trends and hence following suggestions can be given for further research.

- Similar study can be conducted on all the students of CUPB.
- Studies can be conducted by comparing Usage of Social Networking Sites and Anxiety, Stress and Depression among students of CUPB with other universities.
- The study can be undertaken on secondary students or students of other educational institutions.
- Similar study can be undertaken on large population.
- Depth study can also be conducted
- Results of the present study remain good evidences of the efficiency and effectiveness of the tools used.

LIMITATIONS

- The tools adopted for the present study was used as such without any modifications.
- The results of the study lack in external validity as the sample size was not large.
- The study was limited to post graduate students of Central University of Punjab.

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